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Characterisation, X-Ray Diffraction and Microbiological Studies of Complexes Tris(2,2'-bipyridyl)nickel(II) Tungstate Hexahydrate and Tungstatomonoaquobis-(2,2'-dipyridyl)cobalt(II) Monohydrate

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IN our earlier communications^{1,2}, we reported the structural findings on a few complexes of Ni^{II} having unsaturated amines like 1,2-diaminoethane, 1,2-diaminopropane, diethylenetriamine as ligands and WO₄²⁻ as anion. Literature survey reveals that systematic study of tungstate complexes of cobalt and nickel is yet to be completed except for the characterisation of pyridine complexes of Cu^{II} with tungstate, vanadate and molybdate oxoanions³. The aim of the present investigations is to extend the structural studies on the complexing pattern of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with comparatively heavier ligand molecules of 2,2'-bipyridyl in presence of WO₄²⁻ oxoanion. Besides usual structural data it has also been possible to calculate the unit cell parameters on the basis of X-ray powder diffraction patterns of the complexes. In order to evaluate their microbiological significance, their antibacterial activity towards a few plant and human pathogens (*S. typhi*, *B. pumilus*, *S. aureus* and *P. mangiferae*) has also been incorporated.

refluxed on a water-bath with aqueous solution of 2,2'-bipyridyl in molar ratio 1 : 3 for Ni and 1 : 2 for Co for 6–7 h. The solid material dissolved gradually to yield the complex solution. The solutions were concentrated till pink (in case of Ni^{II})/orange (in case of Co^{II}) crystals separated out. The crystals were filtered, washed 3–4 times with a mixture of acetone and water (80 : 20) and recrystallised in double-distilled water. The compounds were dried over P₄O₁₀ before analysis.

Metal contents were estimated gravimetrically both in MWO₄·nH₂O (M=Ni/Co) and also in the corresponding complexes. Ni^{II} was determined as nickel dimethyl glyoxamate and cobalt as tetrapyridine cobalt dithiocyanate by the recommended procedures^{6,7}. Tungsten was estimated as barium tungstate⁸. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were analysed at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. The room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes were determined by Gouy's method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as standard. The X-ray data were recorded on a diffractometer attached to a Phillips X-ray machine using Cu-K_α 1.5418 Å radiation at University of Aberdeen, Scotland (U.K.). The powder diffraction patterns were recorded at a chart speed of 2 cm min⁻¹ and scanning rate of 1° (2θ) cm⁻¹.

Toxicity study : Toxicity study of the complexes was made against four pathogenic bacteria, *Salmonella typhi*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Styphlococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas mangiferae*. Antibacterial

TABLE I—ELEMENTAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF BIPYRIDYL COMPLEXES OF CO^{II} AND NI^{II}

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} * B.M.	Molar conductance $\Omega \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	λ_{max} (cm ⁻¹)	ϵ
		M	N	W				
Ni(C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂) ₃ WO ₄ ·6H ₂ O	Pink	7.04 (6.60)	9.23 (9.52)	19.32 (20.76)	3.12	140.76	19 305 12 224	189 135
Co(C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂)(H ₂ O)(WO ₄)·H ₂ O	Brown	9.95 (8.95)	8.53 (8.54)	28.12 (27.96)	2.51	7.133	22 223 10 800	404 08

*At 298K.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The starting materials NiWO₄·3H₂O and CoWO₄·H₂O were prepared by the reported procedures^{4,5}. Their composition was checked by analyses of Co, Ni and W.

Preparation of complexes : Calculated quantity of powdered MWO₄·nH₂O (M=Ni^{II}/Co^{II}) was

activity of the complexes was determined by standard disc method⁹. The complexes were first sterilised with ethanol, dried and redissolved in sterilised water under aseptic conditions. Sterilised filter paper discs (6 mm) were dipped in the complex solutions. Prior to it the bacteria which were homogenised with nutrient agar media (at 30–35°) were plated into the sterilised petri dishes. Dipped filter paper discs were placed on the seeded medium.

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After 24 h incubation the antibacterial activity was recorded by measuring the inhibition zone against various complexes. Streptomycin solution was taken as control.

Result and Discussion

On the basis of elemental analysis, the molecular formula of nickel complex works out to be $Ni(C_{10}H_8N_2)_3WO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Table 1). The effective magnetic moment of the complex (3.11 B.M.) is in good agreement with the reported values of Ni^{II} complexes in octahedral field (2.92–3.41 B.M.) corresponding to two unpaired electrons^{10,11}. The higher value of molar conductance $140.76 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ is due to the ionic nature of the complex indicating WO_4^{2-} outside the coordination sphere¹². In the electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complex, two absorption bands are found at 12 224 and 19 305 cm^{-1} which could be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ transitions, respectively. This suggests the octahedral geometry of the six-coordinate complex^{13,14}.

On the basis of elemental analysis data the molecular formula of the cobalt complex works out to be $Co(C_{10}H_8N_2)_3WO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$. The molar conductance values suggest that the complex becomes ionic on dissolution in water as a result of the possible salvolysis equilibrium of the type¹⁵,

The observed magnetic moment for the Co^{II} complex (2.51 B.M.) is less than the usual value for the high-spin O_h cobalt complexes. This indicates that the complex could be in a spin-paired O_h geometry¹⁶. The electronic spectra show two absorption bands around 10 800 (weak) and 22 223 cm^{-1} (shoulder), respectively¹⁷. A positive shift in ν_{C-N} and ν_{C-C} stretching could be due to the tightening of the aromatic ring of the bidentate ligand in both the complexes¹⁸⁻²². The absorption due to plane motion of the ring hydrogen lies in the lower region. The negative shift of this band indicates the change in the size and polarising effect inside the coordinate molecule²³. The complex of Ni^{II} shows a broad band around 3 500 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of water of crystallisation^{23,24}. The absorption for tungstate ion in the Ni complex lies at 800–1 000 cm^{-1} ²⁵. The ν_1 and ν_3 bands appear at 908 (medium) and 870 cm^{-1} (shoulder), respectively. The bands at 3 500 (broad), 1 630 (sharp) and 740 cm^{-1} (medium sharp) in the spectra of the cobalt complex indicate the presence of coordinated water molecule and may be assigned to OH stretching, bending and rocking vibrations, respectively^{26,27}. In this complex the ν_1 band for WO_4^{2-} appears at 982 cm^{-1} as a sharp peak. In addition to the ν_1 band, two more bands 910 (sharp) and 860 cm^{-1} (shoulder) due to WO_4^{2-} ion indicate the oxoanion bonded to the central metal in the solid state.

The Table 2 reports the X-ray powder diffraction data on tris(2,2'-bipyridyl)nickel(II) tungstate

hexahydrate and tungstatoaquobis(2,2'-bipyridyl)cobalt(II) monohydrate. The unit cell calculations have been done for the tetragonal symmetry of the Nickel complex. The cell parameters have been calculated by the following equations²⁸⁻³¹.

TABLE 2—POWDER DIFFRACTION DATA FOR Ni^{II} AND Co^{II} COMPLEXES

Peak no.	2θ	Relative intensity $I/I_0 \times 100$	Observed $\sin^2 \theta$	Calculated $\sin^2 \theta$	(hkl)
(i) $Ni(bipy)_3WO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$					
1	7.9	44.4	0.0047	0.0047	(110)
2	10.0	7.5	0.0076	0.0076	(111)
3	11.6	30.6	0.0102	0.0095	(200)
4	12.8	100.0	0.0124	0.0123	(201)
5	14.9	50.6	0.0168	0.0161	(112)
6	16.1	26.7	0.0196	0.0190	(220)
7	17.6	42.2	0.0234	0.0237	(310)
8	19.4	39.8	0.0284	0.0280	(103)
9	19.9	42.2	0.0299	{0.0303 {0.0304	{(222) {(113)
10	20.4	33.4	0.0314	0.0308	(320)
11	22.6	15.5	0.0384	0.0379	(400)
12	23.5	68.7	0.0415	{0.0423 {0.0408	{(322) {(401)
13	24.5	46.7	0.0450	0.0456	(004)
14	26.9	28.9	0.0541	0.0551	(204)
15	27.6	26.4	0.0569	0.0565	(323)
(ii) $Co(bipy)_3(H_2O)(WO_4) \cdot H_2O$					
1	7.9	75.6	0.0047	0.0047	(001)
2	9.1	59.4	0.0063	0.0063	(200)
3	10.6	67.5	0.0085	{0.0085 {0.0084	{(020) {(210)
4	11.7	91.8	0.0104	{0.0101 {0.0110	{(120) {(201)
5	13.3	100	0.0134	{0.0133 {0.0132	{(021) {(211)
6	14.0	51.3	0.0148	{0.0148 {0.0148 {0.0142	{(121) {(220) {(300)
7	14.7	43.2	0.0164	0.0163	(310)
8	16.2	22.9	0.0198	0.0195	(221)
9	17.4	35.1	0.0229	0.0227	(320)
10	18.2	41.8	0.0250	{0.0252 {0.0253 {0.0255	{(400) {(202) {(230)
11	20.0	54.4	0.0301	0.0300	(401)
12	22.3	48.6	0.0374	{0.0384 {0.0382	{(421) {(032)
13	23.6	75.6	0.0418	{0.0411 {0.0417	{(240) {(312)
14	27.0	43.2	0.0545	0.0547	(142)
15	28.2	40.5	0.0593	{0.0593 {0.0588	{(440) {(610)
16	30.0	33.7	0.0670	{0.0672 {0.0679	{(342) {(403)
17	30.7	27.0	0.0701	{0.0701 {0.0699	{(413) {(621)
18	31.9	24.3	0.0755	0.0758	(630)
19	32.9	21.6	0.0802	{0.0797 {0.0805	{(114) {(631)
20	35.1	21.6	0.0909	{0.0908 {0.0904	{(640) {(721)
21	36.8	20.2	0.0996	{0.1006 {0.0994	{(800) {(603)
22	39.8	21.0	0.1158	{0.1159 {0.1147	{(741) {(651)

For tetragonal system :

$$\sin^2 \theta_{(hkl)} = A(h^2 + k^2) + C l^2$$

where, $A = \lambda^2/4a^2$ and $C = \lambda^2/4c^2$.

TABLE 3—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF COMPLEXES OF Ni^{II} AND Co^{II}

Strain	Zone of inhibition (mm)*						Control streptomycin 40 mg ml ⁻¹	
	Ni(bipy) ₂ WO ₄ ·6H ₂ O			Co(bipy) ₂ (H ₂ O)(WO ₄) ₂ ·H ₂ O				
	Concn.	0.01 M	0.05 M	0.1 M	0.01 M	0.05 M		0.1 M
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>		7	12	16	10	16	18	22
<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>		6	10	14	10	12	15	27
<i>Styphlococcus aureus</i>		10	15	20	11	18	21	25
<i>Pseudomonas mangiferae</i>		Nil	Nil	Nil	5	8	16	30

*Including the diameter of filter paper disc.

For orthorhombic system :

$$\sin^2 \theta_{(hkl)} = Ah^2 + Bk^2 + Cl^2$$

where, $A = \lambda^2/4a^2$, $B = \lambda^2/4b^2$, $C = \lambda^2/4c^2$.

The experimental values of $\sin^2\theta$ are in good agreement with the calculated values of $\sin^2\theta$ for tetragonal and orthorhombic cells. These calculations can be summarised as follows : Ni(C₁₀H₈N₂)₂WO₄·6H₂O, $a = 15.8265 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 14.4377 \text{ \AA}$, cell volume = 3616.3540 \AA^3 ; Co(C₁₀H₈N₂)₂(H₂O)(WO₄)₂·H₂O, $a = 19.4353 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 16.6914 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 11.1830 \text{ \AA}$, cell volume = 3627.8095 \AA^3 .

The microbial data (Table 3) reveal that the complexes have a remarkable antibacterial activity against four pathogens, namely *S. typhi*, *B. pumilus*, *S. aureus*, and *P. mangiferae*. The only exception was that Ni(bipy)₂WO₄ does not show activity against *P. mangiferae*. There are two general observations on such studies. The cobalt complex is more toxic than the Ni complex. The microbial activity is a function of the concentration of the compounds. The activity increases with the increase in concentration which is evident from the increased zone of inhibition.

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